

DECREASING ANTI-SOCIAL BEHAVIOUR THROUGH THE ACQUISITION OF ENTREPRENEURIAL SKILL IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN RIVERS STATE.

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Abstract

This study explored the decreasing of anti-social behaviour through the acquisition of entrepreneurial skill in senior secondary schools in Rivers State. It adopted a descriptive survey design. The population of the study consisted of 3000 teachers with a sample size of 300 respondents drawn through stratified random sampling technique. A self-developed instrument was validated by management educators and the reliability yielded a coefficient of 0.70. A modified 4-point Likert rating scale was adopted. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics mean and standard deviation. A z-test statistic was used in testing the hypotheses at 0,05 level of significance. The findings showed that the acquisition of entrepreneurial skill decreases antisocial behaviour in secondary school. Based on the findings, it was then recommended that Government should provide adequate fund for the procurement of the necessary materials needed in the teaching and learning of the technical and vocational based subjects in order to meet the set goal of the National Policy on Education. Students' interest should be tailored towards appreciating vocational subjects to enable them acquire skills for self-reliance as diversion of attention will facilitate the eradication of antisocial behaviours.

Introduction

In every society, behaviour is been structured by social norms. When a behaviour negates completely from the set standard, then it could be termed antisocial. Though, labelling a behaviour antisocial is dependent on the society's values, believes and norms. Actually, what is seen as abnormal antisocial behaviour in one society may be normal in another society. Goode in Bolu-Steeve and Esere (2017) agreed to this assertion by maintaining that, behaviour that is deviant in one society may not be in another. Even in the same society according to him, what may be deviant today may not deviant tomorrow.

However, Anti-social behaviour has been an age-long issue of concern in our society. Recently, this narrative has become overwhelming such that the society can no longer contain it. This aberration is now seen as a normal

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societal value especially among the youths. It is like erosion, eaten deep into the societal norms and values and yet finding its way down to the future generation. Anti-social behaviour is a surge of cruelty, aggression, delinquency and acrimony in all direction and spheres of humanity. Its influence has thrown mankind into a state of confusion, obsessed with fear of the unknown. The menace is a canker worm plaguing societal peace and stimulating unrest. Antisocial behaviour largely is any behaviour that is not in tune with the traditional recognised rules and laws that govern individuals in the society. Antisocial behaviour based on its actions, contradicts the norms and moral expectation of the people. People with antisocial behaviour are known for their criminal activities and they also go against the social standard of the society. Antisocial behaviour is characterised by the following: Impulsive behaviour, low frustration tolerance, inadequate conscience development, irresponsible, lack of worry and guilt, lack of interpersonal relationship and repulsive with authority Nwankwo (2013). Davidoff in Nwankwo (2013) emphasised that, persons with antisocial behaviour are deficient in the sense of right and wrong which is developed at an earlier stage. They do not possess any moral principle; their only concern is on how to manipulate people to get what they want without consideration of other people's feelings. They live in the present and care for immediate gratification. They rarely learn a lesson from punishment. Ronald (2007) affirmed that, children with antisocial behaviour constantly contravene the right of others. They always portray aggression and are hostile to others, intentionally destroy people's property, play truancy at school, escape from home with the slightest provocation, indulge in stealing, rape threaten or may harm their victims.

The environment of a child to a large extent influences the child's behaviour either positively or negatively. A behaviour is positive if it conforms with the societal norms and values while it is negative if it contradicts the standard of the society. The first contact place of the child is the family and first contact persons are the parents and specifically the mother. If the parent adopts the right parenting style, teaching the child morals and societal ethics, scolding the child whenever he or she is wrong, chances of the child developing antisocial behaviour may be slim but lack of adequate parental control and care will lead to non-standard behaviours (Suleiman 2011). The home is a mediator of socialize

However, anti-social behaviour is a psychological problem as well as a personality disorder that disregard and violate peoples right. Students with anti-social behaviour are associated with truancy, stealing, lying, destruction and brutality. They cannot sit down comfortably in the classroom, they are unserious with their studies, always irritable, impulsive, reacts without a thought of the aftermath, engages in frequent belligerent and inability to stay at a place (Andrew, 2020). Anti-social behaviour is a form of conduct that is orally or overtly dangerous to others and the same time negates social prospect of a specific location. Antisocial behaviour as defined by Ines, Ana and Sonia (2020) is a conduct disorder and a tedious and insistent pattern of behaviour in which the rudimentary rights of others are not respected or major suitable societal norm or rules are violated. The increasing rate of disorderliness, misbehaviour and violence in schools today, is as a result of this so called anti-social behaviour among students. A sensible percentage of these students suffer from academic, occupational and social failures (Wilson, 2020). According to Police.uk in Caroline (2018), antisocial behaviour comprised of all intolerable actions of student militating against the society

Antisocial behaviour is a factor that has risen so much eye-brow among people in recent time due to the much pressure and anxiety they have gone through. It is now like wild fire spreading as fast as possible to every nook and cranny of the society. So many lives and properties have been lost to this particular societal ill. Families have been displaced and others abandoning their properties and belonging just to be alive. It has risen to the point such that people are afraid of their own shadows much less speaking out. The level of insecurity precipitating from this menace is quite alarming.

Secondary schools in Nigeria, especially senior secondary schools are not left out. The school is exactly the focal point of the antisocial behaviour. As students from different background converge in school, they form circles which in a way is the basic foundation for the execution of their innate or imitative antisocial behaviours. Students with antisocial behaviours display much trait of indiscipline such as disobedience, disrespect, aggression, temper tantrum and destructive attitude. Clare in Olugbenga (2015) defined antisocial behaviour as an action that are destructive, causes alarm, harassment and distress to one person or another from different homes of families. The

concept describes or refers to behaviour disorder which calls for psychological intervention. This act is majorly exhibited by young people.

Indicators of Antisocial Behaviours

Some of the indicators of antisocial behaviour include:

- Drug abuse
- Rape
- Stealing
- cultism
- Examination malpractice
- Incest
- Aggressiveness
- Anxiety

Causes of Antisocial Behaviour

Mrunal (2017), identified the following causes of antisocial behaviour.

- Home filled with strife and violence: A home where there is no cordial relationship between children and parents, husband and wife are bound to raise children with behavioural problems.
- Faulty parenting style: Parental role in the upbringing of the child is very paramount especially during the first five years of development. Parents who adopt faulty parenting style and are either too rigid or careless in their parenting will expose their children to this disorder. For instance, the laissez-faire parents.
- Genetic factor: Antisocial behaviour could be inherited from parents. If one of the parents is psychopathic, no doubt, the gene may be transferred to their children or one of them.
- Environmental factor: This is another factor that highly stimulates behavioural problems amongst children. The environment the child lives in plays an essential role in building or destroying the child. If the environment is safe, devoid of violence and crime, the tendency of a child turning a psychopath may be slim.
- Biological factor: Some of these abnormalities in children are sometimes traced to biological factors. Ronald (2007) attributed some dysfunctions in behaviour to malformation resulting from mutation of brain chemicals and neurons or malfunctioning of the brain as a result of head injury relating to accident.
- Parental death or separation. Good number of children raised by single parent or foster parent as a result of death or separation of their own parents develop behaviour tantrum.

Ways of checking antisocial behaviour

Antisocial behaviour can be checked through;

- Education
- School counselling
- Introducing entrepreneurial education in secondary schools
- Teaching of conflict resolution in secondary schools
- Dress Code
- Family intervention

Education is a fundamental tool in the economic and national development of a society. It is termed a source of development because it is the yardstick for literacy and the acquisition of skill (Anita, Anan, and Okoro in Amesi and Allen 2019). The role of education in the development of a nation and her citizens is incomparable. A nation that is highly placed educationally, acquires development all round. Through education people can be prepared and acquainted with great skills that will avail them the opportunity for better job on graduation.

Incontrovertibly, for a nation to attain a sustainable development, the involvement their labour force has a great part to play which can only be visible through education. In the same vein, education could be seen as the cradle for innovation, entrepreneurial skills and sophisticated ideas needed to sail a nation to the desired economic shore (researchClue.com).

An overview of Entrepreneurial skill:

The hub of an entrepreneurial skill in every society is value creation. Nwabuama in Undiyaundeye and Ekpungu (2015) explicates entrepreneurial skill as the recognition of the general attributes of businesspersons and how they can be proficient in organisation technique needed for effective performance of persons for long term service of an organisation after the attainment of occupational skills. Entrepreneurial skill is the teaching of knowledge that aids the student to strategize, begin and operate their own business.

Undiyaundeye and Ekpungu (2015) Opines that entrepreneurial skill is that kind of education that has the ability to stem the growth and development of an organisation through vocational and technical training. Ezeani (2012) refers to entrepreneurial education as the philosophy of self-reliance that is concerned with teaching students and equipping them prospective skills adequate to meet with the recent economic challenges. Olawolu and Kaegon in Undiyaundeye and Ekpungu (2015) added that, entrepreneurial skill makes the youth to be responsible and opens them up to real life experiences. The objectives of entrepreneurial skill as highlighted by Undiyaundeye and Ekpungu (2015) is to:

- Serve as propelling force for economic growth and development.
- Propose practical education to youths to aid them to be empowered and self- reliant people in their own way.
- Provide students with sufficient training that will allow them to be creative and innovative as to recognise great business opportunities.
- Decrease the high rate of poverty, insecurity and violence.
- Generate employment opportunities.
- Lessen rural and urban migration
- Reduce the level of antisocial behaviours
- Create smooth transition from tradition to modern industrial economy.

Statement of the Problem

Unruly behaviours in recent time is one of the biggest threats witnessed around the globe that is at the verge of wrecking the society. The rate of antisocial behaviour among students is now beckoning for serious attention. The situation has worsened to the extent that student now harass teachers in the school, some teachers are being beaten up in the process of trying to caution them for bad conducts, some got injured and some others lost their lives to it.

As if it is not enough, the disruptive students become cruel and aggressive to the decent ones, they bully and intimidate their fellow students to act according to their instruction. Antisocial behaviour among students no longer ends within the school but is now carried down to the larger society where it has become a major source of insecurity. The question is, how do we curb this antisocial behaviour among students?

However, the study investigated the decreasing of anti-social behaviour through entrepreneurial skill in senior secondary schools in Nigeria

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study aimed at investigating the decreasing of anti-social behaviour through entrepreneurial skill in senior secondary schools in Rivers State. In specific terms, the study tends to:

- Find out if the acquisition of entrepreneurial skill decreases antisocial behaviour in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Question

- What extent does the acquisition of entrepreneurial skill decrease antisocial behaviour in secondary schools in Rivers State?
- Hypothesis
- There is no significant difference between the mean values of male and female teachers on how the acquisition of entrepreneurial skill decreases antisocial behaviour in secondary schools in Rivers State.
- Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population was made up of 3000 teachers. Male were made up of 1000 while females were 2000. From this a sample size of 300 (100 males and 200 females) representing 10% was drawn using stratified random sampling technique. The instrument for the study was a self-

structured questionnaire titled “Decreasing of Antisocial Behaviour through Entrepreneurial Skill Inventory” (DABESI) which was patterned after modified 4-point Likert’s rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE). The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics mean and standard deviation. The criterion means of 2.50 was used as a yardstick for decision making. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while z-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Research Question 1: What extent does the acquisition of entrepreneurial skill decrease antisocial behaviour in secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 1: analysis of mean ratings of male and female teachers on the extent the acquisition of entrepreneurial skill decreases antisocial behaviour in secondary schools in rivers State.

S/N		Male			Female			XX	Decision
		X	SD	Decision	X	SD	Decision		
	What extent does entrepreneurial skill decrease antisocial behaviour in secondary schools in Rivers State?								
1.	It keeps them busy all day.	3.15	1.31	VHE	3.19	1.33	VHE	3.17	HE
2.	They rarely have time for learning the skill.	1.13	1.09	VLE	2.18	1.13	VLE	1.66	LE
3.	They concentrate more on the skill.	2.79	1.21	VHE	2.86	1.12	VHE	2.83	HE
4.	They are no longer interested in any disruptive behaviour.	2.97	1.25	VHE	2.72	1.20	VHE	2.85	HE
5.	They want to be responsible and earn a living through acquiring skill.	2.89	1.23	VHE	2.86	1.22	VHE	2.88	HE
	Aggregate mean	2.59			2.76			2.68	

The data in table 1 showed the mean scores of male and female teachers on the extent acquisition of entrepreneurial skill decrease antisocial behaviour in secondary schools in Rivers State. For males, items 2 with mean score of 1.13 is below the criterion mean of 2.50. While items 1, 3, 4 and 5 with their mean scores of 3.15, 2.79, 2.97 and 2.89 are above the criterion mean. Likewise, for females, items 2 with mean score of 2.18 respectively is below the criterion mean. While item 1, 3, 4 and 5 with mean scores of 3.19, 2.86, 2.72 and 2.86 are above the criterion mean. For the weighted mean, items 2 with mean score of 1.66 is below the criterion mean while items 1, 3, 4 and 5 with mean scores of 3.17, 2.83, 2.85 and 2.88 are above the criterion mean of 2.50. The aggregate mean of 2.59 for males, 2.76 for females and 2.68 for the weighted mean are all above the criterion mean. This showed that the acquisition of entrepreneurial skill decreases antisocial behaviour in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the mean values of male and female teachers on how the acquisition of entrepreneurial skill decreases antisocial behaviour in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 2: z-test analysis of the significance difference in the mean value of male and female teachers on how the acquisition of entrepreneurial skill decreases antisocial behaviour in Rivers State.

Category	N	X	SD	DF	P	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
male	100	24.05	1.69	298	0.05	0.56	1.96	Accepted
Female	200	22,08	1.76					

The data in table 2 showed that male had a mean and standard deviation of 24.05 and 1.69 while female had mean of 22.08 and 1.76 respectively. The z-calculated value of 0.56 is less than the z-critical value of 1.96 at a degree of freedom of 298 and at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significance difference is accepted. This infers that, there is no significance difference in the mean value of male and female teachers on how the acquisition of entrepreneurial skill decreases antisocial behaviour in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

What extent does the acquisition of entrepreneurial skill decrease antisocial behaviour in secondary schools in Rivers State?

The result of the analysis in table 2 showed that the acquisition of entrepreneurial skill decreases antisocial behaviour in secondary schools in Rivers State. This is in consonance with the findings of Ogundele, Oparinde and Moronfoye (2013) who asserts that skills acquired by students would aid job creation, youth empowerment and poverty mitigation which likely has the capacity to solve various social problems. Ejifor (2010) describes skills as renowned traditions of carrying out activities. Okeke (2005) avows that skill is the act of representing the routine of interim, thinking in such a way that the procedure becomes normal through constant practice. Practical lessons capture the attention of students and as a source of self-reliance, students who are serious and want to be self-actualized, would rather take conscious advantage of such opportunities. There are some vocational subjects introduced or offered in secondary schools that are skill oriented. These subjects need to be strengthened in order to achieve the educational goal.

Acquiring skill involves the three educational domains such as the Cognitive, Affective and psychomotor (Head, Heart and Hand). If entrepreneurial education is introduced in secondary schools, it will occupy students since skill requires absolute concentration and by that, they will have little or no time to engage in irrational acts. According to National Policy on Education, one of the broad aims and objectives of secondary education in Nigeria is to prepare for useful living within the society with its specific objectives which among others include; offering a diversified curriculum to cater for differences in talents, opportunities and future roles, providing technical knowledge and vocational skills necessary for agriculture, industrial, commercial and economic development (FRN in Benson and Felix 2014). The cardinal point of the National policy on education is the education for self-reliance. Mbionwu in Benson and Felix (2014) states that students who attain satisfactory skill have healthier choices to become entrepreneurs after school. In agreement to this, Kikechi, Owano, Ayodo and Ejakait (2013) upholds that skill acquisition provides a platform for high-tech quality in the face of globalisation of the world economy. Akpotowoh and Amahi (2006) affirms that the skill learnt through commercial related subjects encourage skill training and prepare students with the necessary skill to start their own small-scale business. There is much emphasis on skill acquisition because the bedrock of the 6-3-3-4 system of education is self-reliance which will aid the alleviation of antisocial behaviours among students if followed to the later. Skill acquisition at the senior secondary level will enable students who cannot further their education to earn a living

from the skill already acquired. This will not only make them responsible and self-reliant but will also debilitate the antisocial act.

Conclusion:

The family, community, school and government all have their different roles to play in curbing antisocial behaviour among students. The family as the first contact point of the child ought to be firm in their responsibility. Parent's nurture, chastise and reinforce favourable behaviour as such, they are role models and most behave accordingly. Community and school are institutions of modification. The child is influenced by what is obtainable in the environment and school. Children imitate what they see, a conducive environment devoid of social vices, will produce law abiding citizens. The National Policy on Education emphasised so much on skill acquisition and self-reliance. The government should at all times play their role by providing all it takes for the vocational and technical related subjects to be functional. If all these measures are put in place, the narrative will never remain the same.

Recommendations:

Based on the findings of the study, the following suggestions were made.

1. Government should provide adequate fund for the procurement of the necessary materials needed in the teaching and learning of the technical and vocational based subjects in order to meet the set goal of the National Policy on Education.
2. Students' interest should be tailored towards appreciating vocational subjects to enable them acquire skills for self-reliance as diversion of attention will facilitate the eradication of antisocial behaviours.

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